

Autonomously Steering the Young Adults of North Brabant to Safety

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ABSTRACT

As the amount and complexity of technology in cars has evolved unprecedently over the last decades, it will be a matter of time when cars will be able to drive fully autonomous (classified as stage 5 autonomous cars). This development will revolutionize the concept of driving into a safer and more convenient experience. Although there are clear advantages to autonomous vehicles, previous studies indicate that a lot of people are still anxious towards the development. This paper investigates this technological anxiousness under the population of 18 to 25-year old's in North Brabant. The main purpose is to determine what mediating effect education level has on the acceptance of autonomous cars. Within this study, we were unable to find a significant relationship between the two variables, but were able to draw conclusions on the data collected. Building on this, suggestions were made to increase the acceptance of autonomous cars.

INTRODUCTION

The increased amount of technology in cars has brought entertainment, comfort, but most importantly, safety. The frequency of fatalities in crashes has decreased every year since 1985 (Gorzelay, 2018). Although this might imply that road safety is developing hugely, still 1.24 million people die in car crashes annually worldwide and car accidents are still the leading cause of death among people aged 15 to 29 years old (Gresser, 2014). A similar trend can also be spotted in the Netherlands, where most of the deadly car accidents take place in North Brabant among those aged between 18 and 25 years old.

As new developments in technology reach unprecedented levels of complexity, the question if autonomous driving will actually be possible has perished over the last decades. The possible forms

of autonomous mobility are enormous will further increase in the near future. As of now, the autonomous car is predicted to be one of the first serious forms of mobility to become autonomous. Car manufacturers have been investing in autonomous vehicles over the past years and its market is currently estimated at around \$54.23 billion (Richa, 2018), while predictions for 2026 predict a staggering market-value of \$556.67 billion. A lot of these manufacturers are in the race for producing one of the first so-called stage 5 autonomous cars. The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) and the U.S. Department of Transportation's National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) classified six levels of autonomous vehicles (Walch, 2019). In this classification, stage 5 autonomous cars are 'fully autonomous vehicles', the ultimate level of autonomy. This is the first level of autonomy that does not require a driver to be in control at all anymore. For the rest of this paper, the simplified term 'autonomous cars' will be used to indicate these stage 5 autonomous cars.

Fully autonomous vehicles are expected to bring huge advantages to road safety, as the most accidents can be traced back to human behaviour - distraction, alcohol, and reckless driving (Strong Tie Insurance, sd). In contrast to this, a lot of people feel a certain level of anxiety towards autonomous vehicles. Late surveys show that in the United States of America, 71% of Americans are afraid of autonomous vehicles (Eliot, 2019). Public acceptance towards this level of autonomy has not significantly increased with the increased complexity of the associated technology, nor by providing actual proof of the use of the technology in multiple instances.

This research will further investigate the level of acceptance in North Brabant. In 2018, 150 people unfortunately died in car accidents on the roads of North Brabant, causing it to be the most dangerous province in the Netherlands (CBS, 2019). This is a dramatic increase since the year before, where 98 traffic deaths were recorded in the same province.

As it is not the case that North Brabant has the highest amount of road surface, nor the highest number of daily motorists driving on it, reasons for this increase in traffic deaths are still unclear. As 18-25-year olds have the highest risk to be involved in fatal car accidents in the Netherlands (CBS, 2019), they will form the focus for this research. On the assumption that autonomous vehicles will eventually bring these traffic deaths down to close to zero, there is research needed as to whether this group of motorists is anxious towards this technology. The level of education of respondents will be taken into account as previous research has indicated that this variable has a significant effect on the involvement in traffic accidents.

We address missing knowledge on overall acceptance of youths towards autonomous vehicles in North Brabant, and to what extent this acceptance is influenced by education. Building on this, we examine the extent to which provincial policy makers could improve acceptance in this age region. This knowledge can be generalized to future developments in the world of private autonomous mobility vehicles, such as hoverboards, flying cars, and others that could actually be part of the future of travelling. Different organizations and government agencies could very well use this research to address anxiety and successfully introduce new, even more safe ways of travelling.

METHOD

This research originally took off from the empirical view on the amount of traffic deaths in North Brabant, to see if this can be further explained by theoretical research. Existing literature on the overall acceptance of new technological developments is used to understand the concept of acceptance. To determine if these theories would still be valid for the acceptance of autonomous cars, qualitative research is conducted on multiple respondents with a divergent level of education from North Brabant in the ages of 18-25 years old. In these surveys, the respondents were faced with multiple questions measuring their anxiety. For the reason that anxiety is a pretty abstract concept, existing research methods are analysed, adjusted to fit on this complex subject, and used.

The research took place in two structured ways. First, relevant theories regarding the acceptance toward autonomous cars were analysed in a literature research. The literature in this research paper is chosen based on the following criteria; academic title, general characteristics, validity and significance. These criteria helped to find relevant papers using Google Scholar/Worldcat and gained insight into theories that are adding value for conducting further research and making the survey.

To find out if this literature still holds for autonomous cars and within the province of North Brabant, an online survey is conducted. The questionnaire was developed to conduct research about several topics related to autonomous and self-driving vehicles. Some survey items were taken or from previous studies that involved relevant questions and/or used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

The following main topics were included in the survey:

- Familiarity and personal opinion about autonomous cars and/or self-driving vehicles;
- Expected benefits of self-driving vehicles;
- Expected issues of autonomous driving;
- Interest in autonomous cars;
- Self-driving vehicles regarding provincial infrastructure.

Information related to each respondent's demographic information was limited to the education level and age. The three categories in the survey are based on prior research definitions of education level that are mentioned in the paper. The categories are (1) no or lower secondary education, (2) intermediate secondary education or entrance qualification for universities of applied, (3) higher secondary education. This information is useful to identify the relationship between education level and the acceptance towards autonomous cars. The full text of the questionnaire can be found in the appendix. This survey was conducted in November 2019.

Moreover, an online tool was used to target individuals in the age range of 18 to 25 in North Brabant. To be able to create a representative sample out of this slightly specific target audience, social media was used to distribute the survey. The objective is to reach at least 5% of the total population, what makes a total sample size of 10,000 respondents (Brabant Databank).

BACKGROUND

Current literature on anxiety will be divided into technology anxiety and anxiety towards driving. The combination of these two layers of anxiety form a strong fundament for the investigation of acceptance towards autonomous cars. This acceptance will be assessed using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

TECHNOLOGY ANXIETY

In this paper, the review of Craske, M., Rauch, S., Usrano, R., Prenoveau, J., Pine, D. & Zinbarg, R. is being used to clarify the definition of 'anxiety'.

The review asserts that; anxiety is a personal, future-oriented mood with preparation for possible, future negative events (Craske, et al., 2019). New technologies could also lead a kind of anxiety, which is indicated as technology anxiety; where people are afraid for using or even thinking about new technologies. It is essential that the willingness of customers to use new technologies outweighs the anxiety to use it, otherwise new technologies will not be accepted in society (Meuter, Ostrom, Bitner, & Roundtree, 2003). Previous studies in the 90's have shown that 55% of Americans suffered from computer anxiety, also indicated as technophobia (Meuter, Ostrom, Bitner, & Roundtree, 2003). The anxiety impact of new technologies differs per person. The following examples of differences between people or groups are shown in previous papers; people with a positive attitude towards technology were less sensitive for technophobia than people who had a negative attitude towards technology and those who had more computer related experience also suffered less from technophobia (Brosnan, 1999).

Previous papers of computer anxiety are being used in this paper to get a better understanding about the anxiety of new technologies, like autonomous cars. A lot of research is done about computer anxiety in the 90's and Moldafsky, N. & Kwon, I. mentioned the subject as 'a real phenomenon' (Moldafsky & Kwon, 1994). Researchers tried to find correlates of computer anxiety, but the results of the studies were contrary. (Maurer, 1994) revised all previous studies which were trying to correlate experience, age, gender and academic major to computer anxiety. The conclusion of the paper was that it is not known if one of the aforementioned factors influence computer anxiety and it is neither known how to reduce it. However, he did make a model of the development of computer anxiety, in which he stated that the most affecting factor of computer anxiety is the computer experience. A later study from (Brosnan, 1999) stated that the correlations of computer anxiety were: 'perceived ease of use', 'perceived fun' and 'computer self-efficacy', which are also related to computer experience.

ANXIETY TOWARDS DRIVING (VEHOPHOBIA)

Next to technology anxiety, the current fear of driving normal cars also has to be taken into account when analysing the anxiety for driving in autonomous cars. A previous paper showed that people with higher levels of anxiety for driving a car significantly drove more dangerous and caused more crashes (Dula, Adams, Miesner, & Leonard, 2010).

Previous studies have shown several correlations with anxiety when driving a car. The

most obvious factor is experience, an anxious driving style is significantly correlated with the experience of driving in a car (Gwyther & Holland, 2012). Also, other 'negative' factors were taken into account for measuring car driving anxiety. These factors had to do with different driving situations like driving on a motorway, driving during bad weather, lane changing during driving and driving during heavy traffic. These driving situations increased anxiety or even driving avoidance, bad weather was indicated as a driving situation which created the highest anxiety among drivers. Besides the investigation of driving situations, the paper also came to the conclusion that females were more anxious about driving than men, and the age group of 24-64 years old were more anxious about driving than the 18-25 or 65+ year old groups (Gwyther & Holland, 2012).

Another study from New Zealand also researched the anxiety of different driving circumstances between men and women. This research substantiates the mentioned paper before. The biggest fear from the participants in the questionnaire was that they cannot control whether other cars will hit them. The second biggest fear was that people will think that they are a bad driver, but women were more sensitive for this argument than men. The third reason why people were anxious about driving was that the people who were riding with them would get hurt (Taylor & Paki, 2009).

ANXIETY TOWARDS AUTONOMOUS CARS

The amount of experience with driving or with new technologies was indicated as the highest correlated factor for reducing anxiety of driving and technology anxiety (Gwyther & Holland, 2012) (Maurer, 1994).

However, an autonomous car is a different kind of new technology than the emerging computer technology in the 90's. That is because people can have full control over a computer, but no control in an autonomous car. The car drives itself and people have no control or are too late to react when something goes wrong. This uncertainty gives a different kind of technology anxiety for autonomous cars than computer usage (Helldin, Falkman, Riveiro, & Davidsson, 2013).

In addition, anxiety about driving in an autonomous car is different than anxiety for driving in regular vehicles (Olia, Razavi, Abdulhai, & Abdelgawad, 2017). A fully autonomous car controls all driving functions under all negative driving conditions, which were the reason for most people to be anxious when driving in a regular vehicle. People do not have to worry anymore about bad weather, heavy traffic or lane changing while

‘driving’ in an autonomous car.

Hohenberger, C. has done research about anxiety of driving an autonomous car and did a survey under the German population. In one paper he researched whether there is a correlation between gender, age or education level and anxiety of driving in an autonomous car. This research asserts that men are more likely to have positive emotions towards automated cars than women (Hohenberger, Spörrle, & Welpel, 2016). However, people in high accident areas, like North Brabant, have more anxiety for driving or when being a passenger in a car. Especially the people who were involved or had seen an accident were more anxious and it affected their driving behaviour (Mayou, Simkin, & Threlfall, 1991). These high accident areas could also have other correlations for driving in an autonomous car than the correlations which were found in Germany.

TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE

The development of autonomous vehicles is expected to be influenced by the acceptance of the technology itself. Within this acceptance, anxiety plays a contradictory role. Technology acceptance is the adoption and use of new technologies among consumers (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, Consumer Acceptance and Use of Information Technology: Extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, 2012). Various models have been used to determine the acceptance towards autonomous cars. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, 2003) were the most adopted models by researchers to determine the acceptance of this new technology. The TAM and UTAUT were developed to explain technology acceptance and could also be an applicable model for the acceptance of autonomous cars (Rahman, Lesch, & Strawderman, Assessing the utility of TAM, TPB, and UTAUT for advanced driver assistance systems, 2017).

The paper of Nordhoff, S., van Arem, B., & Happee, R. made a new conceptual model (4P Acceptance Model) for the acceptance of driverless 4P vehicles, this model tries to explain, predict, and improve user acceptance of driverless vehicles (Nordhoff, 2016). The model links two technology acceptance models, which are the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Technology use (UTAUT) and the Pleasure-Arousal-Dominance-Framework (PAD), with several external variables.

For this paper the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) will be used, because it is the most frequently adopted model by researchers and it has

been proven capable of explaining the acceptance towards autonomous cars best (Nordhoff, 2016). The 4P Acceptance Model take more factors into account to determine the acceptance, but the model has not been tested yet (Rahman, Strawderman, & Carruth, 2017).

Figure 1: Technology Acceptance Model

Studies built on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), have found that people’s degree of acceptance varies by individual characteristics, with younger, male, or more tech savvy people generally more interested in using self-driving cars than older, female, or less tech savvy people (Raue, et al., 2019). In another study, most people were willing to accept automated features that assisted the driver while the driver remained in control, but fewer people were comfortable with full automation (Lee, et al., 2018).

Higher levels of anxiety reduce the intention to accept the 5 autonomous cars among consumers (Hohenberger, Spörrle, & Welpel, 2017). The paper asserts that showing a positive evaluation of benefits to people will decrease the level of anxiety and thus improve the acceptance. People with low levels of self-enhancement happen to be more anxious when it comes to the subject of autonomous cars. That is why values should be triggered within this group when promoting the usage of autonomous cars, to improve the acceptance.

LEVEL OF EDUCATION

To be able to further examine the possible effect of education on the acceptance of autonomous cars, the definition of education should be assessed first. Since previous research defined the level of education differently, a conclusion should be made as to what definition fits this research best. Therefore, several papers regarding the level of education are examined.

Rammstedt, Goldberg, and Borga define the level of education in their research on the significant difference of the Big Five personality traits (Rammstedt, Goldberg, & Borg, 2010). The researchers split education level into three distinct groups: (1) no or lower secondary education; (2)

intermediate secondary education or entrance qualification for universities of applied sciences; and (3) higher secondary education, i.e. those with an entrance qualification for general universities or with a university degree.

Another research, regarding health expectancy in Finland, classifies the level of education level on three different levels as well. The first group was classified as basic education or less: persons whom no educational degrees are registered belong to this class. The second group were secondary educated people: persons with a vocational training as well as persons with an upper secondary school certificate but without further training. The last and third group were higher educated people: persons with institute- or university-level certificates or degrees (Valkonen, Sihvonen, & Lahelma, 1997).

Melissa Alexander, Steven Weiss, Darren Braude, Amy A. Ernst, and Lynne Fullerton-Gleason regard the relationship between the level of education and degree of commitment. The researchers define 'level of education' into the following three groups: (1) certificate level, (2) associate's or bachelor's degree, (3) and beyond the bachelor's degree level (Alexander, Weiss, Braude, Ernst, & Fullerton-Gleason, 2009).

For this research, education is defined on the three distinct groups of Beatrice Rammstedt, Lewis R. Goldberg, and Ingwer Borga. The definition of the level of education within this research is strongly applicable to the Dutch educational system, which has great similarities to the German system of education.

EFFECT OF EDUCATION ON TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE

For many years, researchers have been interested in identifying the conditions or factors that facilitated technology acceptance among users. Over time, models were developed and tested to predict these factors and conditions. Of all these models, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) appears arguably the most popular model (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, User Acceptance of Computer Technology: A Comparison of Two Theoretical Models, 1989). The model has been empirically proven capable of explaining user behaviour, and specifies the causal relationships between perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude towards computer use, and behavioural intention (Teo, 2009)

Researchers Koul, S. and Eydgahi, A. have shown that the technology acceptance model is usable for measuring driverless car technology adoption (Koul & Eydgahi, 2018). The researchers

examined the relationship between perceived usefulness of driverless car technology, perceived ease of use of driverless car technology, years of driving experience, age and the intention to use driverless cars. This study found a significant positive relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and the intention to use driverless cars. Also, there were significant negative relationships between years of driving experience, age and intention to use driverless cars (Koul & Eydgahi, 2018).

Research stated that there is a small amount of significant identifying factors that influence the acceptability of smart devices (Zhan, Zukerman, & Partovi, 2018). These user-related factors include demographic features, such as age, gender, level of education and cultural background. Another research tested the relationship between individual difference variables, e.g. level of education, and information system usage (Burton-Jones & Hubona, 2006). According to the combination of these papers, it can be concluded that education level is a significant factor in measuring technology acceptance.

The research shows that people with higher technical expertise and experience with devices were more accepting the devices than people with low/medium expertise and lower experience (Zhan, Zukerman, & Partovi, 2018). Additionally, another paper showed that the level of education influenced the users' success in using IT. According to Burton-Jones & Hubona, a higher education should also improve users' attitude towards technology as well as reduce the anxiety towards it (Burton-Jones & Hubona, 2006).

It can be concluded that the level of education is a strong measure regarding traffic safety and technology acceptance. As people are increasingly educated, their involvement in (deadly) road accidents decreases, indicating a certain difference in safety attitudes. As a consequence, it is expected that anxiety towards autonomous vehicles will differ among these levels. Whereas the acceptance of overall technology has been researched before, the significant differences in driving behaviour, the use of this specific technology, could strongly affect public acceptance.

EFFECT OF EDUCATION ON ROAD SAFETY

Level of education is strongly relevant to this paper because of its significant correlation with traffic accidents. Marie Hasselberg, Marjan Vaez and Lucie Laflamme state that educational levels are dramatic predictors of involvement in accidents (Hasselberg, Vaez, & Laflamme, 2005). This is further explained by David Shinar, Edna

Schechtman, and Richard Compton, showing that the level of education influences the cognitive component of safe driving attitudes (Shinar, Schechtman, & Compton, 2001). Another research based on motor vehicle occupant’s death rate shows that the level of education has an influence on death rates in traffic (Braver, 2003). According to the combination of these theories, it can be concluded that education level is a significant factor in measuring safety consciousness of drivers.

Drivers with a relatively low educational attainment, translated to the ‘no or lower education level’ from the previously defined measure of education, are at a greater risk of severe injuries, and show excess risks of crashes of all kinds (Hasselberg, Vaez, & Laflamme, 2005). When corrected to the annual miles driven, there is no difference in this relation. This is supported by Braver, who found higher mortality rates per unit of travel among people with low levels of education (Braver, 2003). This correlation still holds after controlling the reported seat-belt use of respondents, as educated people are generally expected to be more safety conscious.

This effect is even stronger for relatively young drivers, especially for those with low levels of education. This group has the highest probability of being involved in any type of road accident (Hasselberg, Vaez, & Laflamme, 2005).

RESULTS

Before turning to the acceptance of autonomous cars, an examination is made whether the youth of North-Brabant is known with the technology. Overall, about 90% of the respondents had heard of autonomous cars before. This strengthens the conclusions drawn from the survey data, because the technology is not completely new to most of the respondents.

Overall, the young adults of North Brabant have a relatively positive opinion towards autonomous vehicles. Only 6.9% are somewhat negative about the technology. Within this category, it’s notable that 50% had never heard of autonomous vehicles before. This is clearly more than the people who were more positive about autonomous cars. Only 3% of the people from these more positive categories had never heard of autonomous cars before. This can be derived from figure 2 on the next page.

Figure 2: Opinion towards autonomous driving

This positive image of autonomous cars is mainly driven by the indicated benefits of it. Most of it surfaced around crashes as fewer crashes, reduced severity of crashes, and improved emergency response to crashes are the best-rated categories of benefits. These are highly linked to an increase in safety and are therefore called ‘safety benefits’. On the other hand, autonomous driving offers so-called ‘convenience benefits’, divided into less traffic congestion and a shorter travel time. Young adults clearly address less value to this category, as one respondent perfectly described it: “Nice to have, but it would not convince me enough on itself”. The last category of benefits is classified in value between the upper two. Whereas autonomous cars are overall more expensive than non-autonomous vehicles, this category focusses on the ‘financial benefits’ over time. Better fuel economy and lower insurance rates are picked over convenience benefits as they deliver tangible value to the drivers. When people purchase a car, one of the first things looked at is price. This is no different for autonomous cars. This clear distinction between people’s opinion and the actual amount of money they would pay for an autonomous car can be concluded from the following results. It is gathered on the question if people are interested in paying extra in order to have an autonomous car. As more than 90% of respondents have a positive opinion about autonomous cars, less than 50% agrees to pay additionally for it. This is clearly visualised in figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Willingness to pay for an autonomous car

The general opinion of people towards autonomous driving tends to be more positive than negative, but heavily influenced by the price of it.

However, people are still severely concerned about autonomous cars. Only 3.45% indicated to be not at all concerned about autonomous cars, meaning that 96.55% of the respondents were at least slightly concerned about it. Within this group, almost 90% of the people are moderately or very concerned.

Figure 4: Concern about autonomous cars

Again, most of this concern originates from safety consequences. Safety consequences of equipment failure or system failure, system security (from hackers), and vehicle security (from hackers) are the main concerns of young people in North Brabant.

INFLUENCE OF EDUCATION LEVEL

The results do not offer a relationship between education level and acceptance as strong as previous research does. Although education level is not found to be a significant factor to the variables of interest, some careful results towards this subgroup can be presented.

In general, higher educated people are more likely to be concerned about autonomous cars. More than 50% of the people with at least intermediate secondary education say to be moderately or very concerned about the development. This lies in contrast with the people with no or lower secondary education, where no respondents say to experience the same level of concern. All of the respondents in this category are only slightly concerned with autonomous cars, which is overall an under average amount of concern. See figure .. for an overview.

Figure 5: Concern divided into education levels

When analysing the various benefits of autonomous cars, another pattern can be observed. As resulted from one of the previous paragraphs, people are generally more tempted to be convinced by one of the so-called safety benefits of autonomous driving. This especially holds true for the higher educated people with intermediate secondary education and those with a higher secondary education. In the category ‘No or lower secondary education’, people were relatively more tempted to rely on the convenience and financial benefits rather than the safety benefits.

INFRASTRUCTURAL POLICYMAKERS

The last part of the survey focused on potential actions of infrastructural policymakers to address concern and anxiety towards autonomous cars. Respondents were faced with multiple considerations between two possible actions and were able to indicate which of the two would increase their acceptance best. This paragraph classifies each action from most impact (1) to no or minimal impact (6).

1. Improve the clarity and overall safety of junctions and roundabouts;
2. More adequately lay salt in cold temperatures;
3. Reduce the chances of aquaplaning on highways;
4. Replace junctions with roundabouts;

5. Improve lighting of streets and highways;
6. Improve the condition of asphalt.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

As autonomous cars enter North Brabant, the higher-educated people will be less likely to accept them at first. We expect this discrepancy to be caused by a higher level of awareness of the dangers of the vehicles. Along with this, higher educated people are statistically less likely to be involved in car accidents than lower educated people. This could affect the need for self-driving technology, as they already drive very safely in comparison to others. For the lower educated, this works the other way around: because they are more likely to be involved in any car accident, they tend to be more interested in technology that reduces this risk.

This should be addressed by infrastructural policymakers in two possible ways. At first, lower educated people should be actively informed about the possible risks of autonomous vehicles, due to their current lack of awareness. As they clearly see the advantages of a shorter travel time, less traffic congestion, better fuel economy and lower insurance rates, they fail to see the risks attached to it. On the other hand, higher educated people are less likely to accept autonomous vehicles. Infrastructural policymakers could address this anxiety towards the risks of autonomous driving by enforcing a strict policy for car manufacturers, guaranteeing the quality of the autonomous technology. Secondly, the infrastructural policy makers could create a clear regulatory framework in combination with the government for who is responsible for the damage that could result from an accident. By these two measures, both primary causes of anxiety are taken away. People are guaranteed that the autonomous cars are of excellent quality and they are not responsible for any technological causes.

These results can be generalized into wider developments in the world of private autonomous mobility vehicles. These vehicles all serve the same purpose to travel a certain distance and mostly differ in form. Whether someone travels in an autonomous car or an autonomous hoverboard, anxiety and social acceptance will be similarly. A lot of attention should be paid to assure both consequences by infrastructural policymakers, especially to higher educated people. Whereas technology overall would be more likely to be accepted by higher educated people, the contradictory is true for autonomous cars. Developments in the world of private autonomous mobility vehicles therefore should focus less on educating the lower-educated people on the technology, but should focus on assessing the anxiety of higher educated people towards the safety

of private autonomous mobility vehicles.

Building onto to the ability to generalize the findings to a broader category of autonomous vehicles, we can generalize the results to the other provinces in the Netherlands as well. Youths in other provinces are believed to have equal amounts of anxiety towards private autonomous mobility vehicles. Cultural differences between the provinces of the Netherlands are therefore limited regarding to the acceptance of this development.

LIMITATIONS

Limitations of the research were primarily due to time restrictions. To be able to reach the sample objective, the researchers were obliged to use an online survey method. This restricted a further insight in the underlying causes of anxiety towards autonomous vehicles. To improve the internal validity of the conclusions, further research could build on this by conducting more qualitative research methods. This involves more detailed research in the possible actions policymakers could undertake, to initially shape future policies. The last limitation of this research regards to the sampling method used: the number of respondents reached and the limited variety in respondents of the survey. Due to the lack of time, the researchers were unable to address more than 30 respondents through convenience sampling. These respondents were mainly addressed through social media, which caused an underrepresented of the lower-educated in the results. Further research should pay more attention in addressing all education levels equally.

As technology improves greatly, more and more of the forms of mobility we know today will become autonomous in the near future. Further research could address not only private autonomous mobility vehicles, but could focus on anxiety towards a broader category of autonomous vehicles that are not necessarily private owned. This category involves autonomous private and public mobility as a whole. This research is unable to generalize to this broader category of autonomous vehicles because there is a difference in responsibility and anxiety. Whereas people are anxious for the damage done by their private autonomous vehicles, responsibility for public autonomous vehicles lays elsewhere. Therefore, anxiety and technology acceptance needs further research on this broad category of autonomous vehicles.

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